

**5 SINIF TEXNOLOGIYA DARSLARIDA “MATERIALLARGA ISHLOV
BERISH BO‘LIMI” NI INNOVATSION PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR
ASOSIDA O‘QITISH METODIKASINI
TAKOMILLASHTIRISH**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ta’limda ilg‘or pedagogik va yangi axborotlar texnologiyalarini tatbiq etish o‘quv mashg‘ulotlarining samaradorligini oshiribgina qolmay, ilm-fan yutuqlarini amaliyotda qo‘llash orqali mustaqil va mantiqiy fikrlaydigan, har tomonlama barkamol yuksak ma’naviyatli shaxsni tarbiyalashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Umumta’lim maktablarida texnologiya fanini o‘qitishda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish, texnologiya fanini yanada rivojlantirish, 5 sinf “Materiallarga ishlov berish bo‘limi” bo‘yicha ta’lim jarayonida zamonaviy o‘qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish va ta’lim jarayonida qo‘llay olish bir nechta tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Tayanch so‘zlar: *Ilg‘or texnologiya, texnologik xarita, pedagogik texnologiyalar, innovatsiya, interfaol metodlar.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ “ОТДЕЛУ ОБРАБОТКИ МАТЕРИАЛОВ” НА УРОКАХ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ 5 КЛАССА НА ОСНОВЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Внедрение прогрессивных педагогических и новых информационных технологий в образование не только повышает эффективность обучения, но и через практическое применение достижений науки приобретает важное значение в воспитании самостоятельной и логически мыслящей, всесторонне развитой высокодуховной личности. Использование инновационных педагогических технологий при преподавании предмета технология в общеобразовательных школах, дальнейшее развитие предмета технология, совершенствование современной методики преподавания в образовательном процессе 5 класса “кафедра материаловедения” и возможность применения в образовательном процессе разработаны несколько рекомендаций.

***Ключевые слова:** передовая технология, технологическая карта, педагогические технологии, инновации, интерактивные методы.*

**IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE "MATERIAL
PROCESSING DEPARTMENT" ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE
PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN 5 GRADE TECHNOLOGY CLASSES**

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ABSTRACT

The implementation of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of training, but is also important in the upbringing of an independent and logically thinking, comprehensively competent high-morale person by applying the achievements of Science in practice. Several recommendations have been developed on the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in teaching technology in secondary schools, the further development of Technology Science, improvement of modern teaching methodology in the educational process on the 5th grade “material processing department” and the ability to apply it in the educational process.

Base words: *advanced technology, technological map, pedagogical technologies, innovation, interactive methods.*

The role of the education system in accelerating the socio-economic development of our country and ensuring its economic security is incomparable. Among the global trends such as the internationalization of education, the international mobility of students, the rapid change of the educational program, the issue of ensuring the quality of education is gaining special importance. Modern socio-economic conditions and the high demands placed on the spiritual-ethical, intellectual and professional potential of future specialists put the task of training quality personnel who can meet international

requirements before educational institutions. In order to fulfill these tasks, it is necessary to use innovative pedagogical technologies in education.

Pedagogical technology is a system of modern organization of the educational process, which ensures the necessary quality of education and meets the requirements of accelerated scientific and technical development, aimed at the improvement of educational forms, teaching processes with techniques and It is a consistent method of creation and implementation in human factors, through their joint actions. The use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process is the demand of the times.

Innovation (English) means innovation, innovation, technology is derived from the Greek words "technos" - art, skill and "logos" - science, innovative pedagogical technology is the forms and methods of education. and includes a new approach to methods.

Innovative technologies - by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process, serve to activate the learning of students and develop their personal qualities. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the efficiency of the lesson and is divided into the following criteria, the criteria that serve to increase the efficiency of the lesson have been developed:

- the opportunity to conduct informal discussions, to express and express this material freely, the number of lectures is small, and the number of seminars, on the contrary, is large, to create opportunities for students to take initiative;

- giving tasks for working in small and large groups, as a class team, completing written works and applying them to the educational process is one of the urgent issues of today. Innovative technologies are the pedagogical process and the introduction of innovations and changes in the activities of teachers and students. Any reforms, innovations, and investments in the education system are undoubtedly aimed at improving the effectiveness of education and making it fully responsive to modern educational requirements.

During the past years, "Technology" lessons have been taught for a long time, that is, from the first grade to the last grade. "Technology" classes in general education schools are organized in three stages, the purpose of which is to properly develop students from the physical side, to familiarize them with the world of work and its people, tools and practices, the main areas of production and professions, used to use work tools, create work skills related to making simple items, orient them to consciously choose a profession, today, on the contrary, a modern system of education has been developed in general education schools.

The basis of the modern education system is a high-quality and high-tech environment. Its creation and development is technically complex, but such an environment serves to improve the educational system, to introduce innovative information and communication technologies in the educational process, and to develop science and technology. Basic knowledge of the properties of wood, their planing, alignment, sawing, drilling, tools, new techniques and progress A number of topics are discussed, such as the fundamentals of technology, basic knowledge of the properties of metals, planning, processing, finishing works, and the creation and use of technological maps.

Therefore, in the technology lessons taught in general education schools, students are explained the production process, production areas, the equipment and mechanisms-machines used in it, their types and use on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies, and different views The process of making items is taught step-by-step based on the available multimedia programs. As a result of this, it is planned to acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications for guiding young people to the profession, and to form the ability to apply them in life.

The organization of classes in technology classes based on modern innovative pedagogical technologies, the availability of modern-looking equipment designed for the performance of certain types of work in modern-looking educational workshops leads to a higher result of the quality of education possible.

Figure 2. Educational workshop "Technology" in innovative education.

As a result of the reforms carried out in any educational system, the teaching of technology lessons taught in general education schools on the basis of electronic resources, software educational tools, and modern educational technologies has a good effect. The 5th grade forms students innovative knowledge, necessary skills and various component skills based on the teaching of the material processing section of the technology science.

In short, the wide use of innovative pedagogical technologies in technology classes, computer classes, subject samples, for example: subject models and layouts, technological maps, tools prepared in multimedia programs, didactic materials on a large scale, in the course of the lesson, will improve the quality of the lesson process. and ensures that it is effective.

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